

Association between Mobile Phone Use before Sleep and Insomnia

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Citation: Nadiyah Younis, Mohammed Alwatari A, Mohammed Alghannami, Mohammed Alhusseini, Noor Al-Wattary, Maryam Alwattary. Association between Mobile Phone Use before Sleep and Insomnia. *Ann Case Rep Clin Stud.* 2025;4(7):1-2.

Received Date: 04 July 2025; **Accepted Date:** 10 July 2025; **Published Date:** 12 July 2025

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ABSTRACT

Mobile phone overuse, particularly before bedtime, has become a growing health concern. This study examined the link between nighttime phone use and insomnia among Iraqis. A cross-sectional survey of 205 participants was conducted using a structured questionnaire covering mobile use, sleep quality, and related symptoms. Results showed a strong association between bedtime phone use and difficulty falling asleep, especially among young females. Excessive use was also tied to headaches, fatigue, anxiety, and sadness. These findings align with global evidence on the harmful effects of nighttime screen exposure and highlight the need for healthier mobile habits to improve sleep and overall well-being.

Keywords: Mobile phone, Sleep, Anxiety, Headache, Insomnia

INTRODUCTION

Mobile phones have become essential to daily life, especially among youth. By 2016, global mobile phone subscriptions exceeded 7.5 billion—surpassing the world’s population at the time ^[1, 2]. While mobile phones facilitate communication and access to information, their overuse has raised serious public health concerns, particularly related to sleep behavior and psychological well-being.

Scientific studies indicate that prolonged mobile phone use—especially exceeding five hours per day or usage within one hour before sleep—is significantly associated with insomnia and poor sleep quality. Electronic media usage at night disrupts sleep by shortening its duration, prolonging sleep onset, and increasing overall sleep deficiency. A dose–response relationship has been observed: the more an individual uses their phone before bedtime, the more likely they are to suffer from sleep loss. Research also suggests that bedtime screen use may account for 4% to 11% of the increase in insomnia and daytime fatigue ^[3, 4, 5].

Sleep regulation involves three main factors: the homeostatic drive, the circadian rhythm, and behavioral patterns. Mobile phone use primarily influences behavioral mechanisms by delaying sleep, increasing cognitive stimulation, and causing emotional arousal. Moreover, exposure to blue light from screens suppresses melatonin production, further disrupting sleep cycles [6, 7].

Mobile phones are frequently used at bedtime, with more than half of respondents in multiple studies reporting that they sleep with their phones nearby. This habit is associated with poor sleep quality, insomnia, and next-day fatigue. Females appear particularly affected, likely due to greater phone dependence and a preference for social interaction during evening hours [8, 9].

In Iraq, mobile phone ownership reached 95% in 2019, with over 37 million users^[10]. Despite this high penetration rate, there is limited data on how mobile phone use affects sleep in Iraqi society. This gap in regional research limits public health efforts aimed at reducing technology-related sleep disorders.

Research Gap and Rationale

Although international evidence supports the link between mobile phone use and sleep disturbances, few studies explore this issue within the cultural and behavioral context of Iraq. Given the nation's rapidly growing mobile user base and rising youth population, it is critical to investigate these associations locally to inform awareness campaigns and behavioral interventions.

Research Objectives

This study aims to:

1. Examine the association between bedtime mobile phone use and insomnia in the Iraqi population.
2. Identify related symptoms such as fatigue, headache, sadness, and anxiety.
3. Determine demographic factors, particularly age and gender, that contribute to sleep disruption related to mobile phone usage.

METHOD

Research Design and Participants

This study used a descriptive, cross-sectional design to assess the relationship between mobile phone use before sleep and insomnia among the general Iraqi population. A total of **205 participants** were enrolled through an online self-administered survey shared via digital platforms. Inclusion criteria included individuals aged 12 and above, residing in Iraq, and consenting to participate voluntarily. No exclusion criteria based on gender or occupation were applied.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument used was a structured, closed-ended questionnaire developed by the authors. The questionnaire included sections covering:

- Demographic data (age, gender)
- Mobile phone use (duration, timing, and bedtime use)
- Sleep quality indicators (sleep onset, duration, interruptions)
- Daytime symptoms (tiredness, anxiety, sadness, and headaches)

The tool was pilot-tested for clarity and refined before data collection. The questionnaire is presented in (Table 1).

Table 1. The online questionnaire for every participant

Question	Answer choices				
Age	5 to 20y	21 to 40y	41 to 60y	61 to 80y	
Gender	Male	female			
How many hours do you use your mobile per day?	Less than 1h	Between 1 to 4h	More than 4h		
Do you use your mobile 1 hour Before sleep?	Yes	No			
How many hours do you sleep a day?	Less than 6h	Between 6 to 9h	More than 9h		
Do you find it hard to fall asleep?	Yes	No			
Do you have an Interrupted sleep?	Yes	No			
Do you have any daytime sadness, anxiety or tiredness due to lack of sleeping? Be specific.	Yes, sadness	Yes, anxiety	Yes, tiredness	no	Yes, I have them all
Do you have any Headache related to	Yes	No	Maybe		

mobile phone					
use?					

Data Collection Procedure

The survey was distributed via online platforms (e.g., WhatsApp, Telegram, and email), ensuring accessibility and wide coverage. Participation was anonymous and voluntary. All participants provided digital consent before proceeding. Ethical approval was granted by the **Baghdad College of Medicine** ethics committee.

Data Analysis

Collected data were coded and entered into IBM SPSS Statistics version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. The Chi-square test was applied to assess the relationships between mobile phone usage patterns and sleep-related variables. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant

RESULT

A total of 205 participants completed the survey. The majority (68.4%) reported using their mobile phones for more than 4 hours per day, while fewer than 3% used their phones for less than 1 hour. **(Figure 1)** illustrates the distribution of daily mobile phone usage among participants.

How many hours do you use your mobile per day ?

206 responses

Figure (1): proportion of people who use mobile by hours daily.

The highest mobile phone usage was found among females aged 5 to 20 years. These participants were significantly more likely to use mobile phones for over 4 hours or within 1 hour before sleep ($p < 0.05$). This relationship between usage and age is shown in **(Table 2)**, and usage by gender in **(Table 3)**.

Table 2: Relationship between mobile phone use more than 4h a day or 1h before sleep and age.

Crosstab					
			Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep		Total
			Yes	No	
Age	5 to 20 year	Count	90	5	95
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	48.6%	23.8%	46.1%

Table 3: Relationship between mobile phone use more than 4h a day or 1h before sleep and gender.

Crosstab					
			Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep		Total
			Yes	No	
Gender	Male	Count	68	14	82
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	36.8%	66.7%	39.8%
	Female	Count	117	7	124
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	63.2%	33.3%	60.2%
Total		Count	185	21	206
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Participants who reported high mobile phone use—either more than 4 hours daily or within 1 hour before sleep—were significantly more likely to report difficulty falling asleep ($p < 0.05$), which is one of the key signs of insomnia. This relationship is presented in **(Table 4)**.

Table 4: Relationship between mobile phone use more than 4h a day or 1h before sleep and difficult sleep onset.

Crosstab					
			Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep		Total
			Yes	No	
Do you find it hard to fall asleep ?	Yes	Count	114	5	119
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	61.6%	23.8%	57.8%
	No	Count	71	16	87
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	38.4%	76.2%	42.2%
Total		Count	185	21	206
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

In terms of associated symptoms, 41.5% of these participants reported headaches they attributed to mobile phone use. Another 33.2% said they might be experiencing headaches for the same reason. (Figure 2) presents the distribution of headache symptoms in relation to mobile phone usage.

Figure (2): association between headache and mobile phone use

Do you have any headache related to mobile phone use ?

205 responses

Daytime symptoms including tiredness (23%), sadness (14%), and anxiety (11%) were commonly reported among high-use participants. Notably, 33% of respondents indicated experiencing all three symptoms. These findings are summarized in (Table 5).

Table 5: relationship between mobile phone use more than 4h a day or 1h before sleep and daytime sadness, anxiety or tiredness.

Crosstab					
			Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep		Total
			Yes	No	
Do you have any daytime sadness, anxiety or tiredness due to lack of sleeping ? Be specific.	Yes tiredness	Count	44	6	50
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	23.8%	28.6%	24.3%
	Yes sadness	Count	27	1	28
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	14.6%	4.8%	13.6%
	Yes anxiety	Count	21	1	22
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	11.4%	4.8%	10.7%
	Yes I have them all	Count	61	1	62
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	33.0%	4.8%	30.1%
	No	Count	32	12	44
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	17.3%	57.1%	21.4%
Total		Count	185	21	206
		% within Use phone more than 4 hours or use it 1 hour before sleep	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-square analysis confirmed significant relationships between bedtime phone use and difficulty sleeping, emotional symptoms, and demographic variables. These findings support the hypothesis that excessive mobile phone use, particularly at night, is strongly associated with insomnia and related physical and emotional symptoms.

DISCUSSION

Among the 205 participants in this study, we found that the largest group of mobile phone users—and those most prone to excessive use—were females between the ages of 5 and 20. This aligns with previous research showing that females tend to be more dependent on mobile phones, particularly for interpersonal communication and emotional

interaction. Ibrahim et al. (2018) similarly reported higher phone addiction among female medical students in Saudi Arabia, attributing this to increased social media engagement and emotional connectivity [9, 10, 11].

Our results also showed that using a mobile phone for more than 4 hours a day or within 1 hour before sleep was significantly associated with difficulty falling asleep, a key symptom of insomnia. This supports earlier findings by Exelmans and Van den Bulck (2016), who observed that bedtime mobile phone use in adults was directly linked to poorer sleep quality, delayed sleep onset, and increased fatigue [8]. Likewise, Liu et al. (2019) and Tamura et al. (2017) documented how prolonged screen exposure negatively impacts circadian rhythms, sleep efficiency, and overall sleep satisfaction [2, 3].

Another study said that the addiction level was determined to be higher in second-year students (20 years), those with poor family income, those with type A personality, and those whose age for first mobile phone is 13 and below [12].

We further found that more than 40% of participants who used their phones extensively reported headaches that they attributed to this behavior, and another 33.2% suspected a possible connection. These findings mirror those of Wang et al. (2017), who reported a 38% increased risk of headaches among mobile phone users compared with non-users [13].

The mechanisms proposed include electromagnetic exposure, postural stress, and prolonged mental stimulation.

Additionally, a significant proportion of participants reported experiencing daytime fatigue (23%), sadness (14%), and anxiety (11%), with 33% reporting all three symptoms together. These psychological and emotional responses are likely related to sleep deprivation caused by late-night phone use. El-Sayed Desouky and Abu-Zaid (2020) confirmed a strong correlation between problematic mobile phone use and increased levels of depression and anxiety in young adults [14]. Our findings extend this by demonstrating that the overlap of emotional and physical symptoms is notably high in younger Iraqi users, suggesting a cumulative impact of poor sleep, psychological strain, and overexposure to screen-based content.

Compared to other studies conducted in Western or Asian populations, our study contributes new regional data specific to Iraq, where mobile phone penetration has rapidly increased, now exceeding 95% of the population [10]. While the patterns observed are globally consistent, our findings are particularly important in highlighting how these issues manifest in a Middle Eastern, post-conflict society with unique social, cultural, and economic dynamics.

Our data support a growing body of evidence linking mobile phone overuse to a spectrum of health concerns, particularly sleep disturbance and its consequences. However, the demographic insights—such as the heightened risk among young females—offer direction for targeted interventions. Health education campaigns in schools and universities should emphasize digital wellness and promote healthier bedtime routines.

While our findings are robust, they are based on self-reported data, which can introduce recall or response bias. Furthermore, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits causal interpretations. Future research with longitudinal designs or objective sleep tracking could provide deeper insights into the temporal relationship between phone use and insomnia symptoms.

In summary, this study confirms a strong relationship between mobile phone use before sleep and insomnia-related symptoms among Iraqi youth, particularly females. It contributes valuable local data to a globally relevant issue and underscores the importance of culturally sensitive interventions aimed at promoting better digital habits and sleep hygiene.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates a clear link between mobile phone use before sleep and insomnia, particularly among young Iraqi females. Bedtime phone use was associated with difficulty falling asleep, headaches, and emotional symptoms such as anxiety and sadness. These findings address the research objectives by identifying the behavioral impact of mobile overuse and highlighting at-risk groups. By contributing region-specific data, the study adds to the global understanding of sleep disturbances and supports the need for culturally relevant awareness and prevention strategies within behavioral and health psychology.

Suggestion

Awareness programs should educate youth, especially females, on the effects of pre-sleep mobile phone use. Schools and healthcare providers should promote healthier bedtime habits to reduce **insomnia**. Future research should explore long-term effects and evaluate tailored intervention strategies.

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